

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: DALI****FIRST NAME: SERGE****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author ~~x~~ did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 11%

The author used the following software: Microsoft 350 on Windows 10

List your 5 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. Essay Writing (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 6-12)
2. Punctuations (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 15-23)
3. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 33-39)
4. Style Guide and Use of Chicago Style (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 40-56)
5. Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 58-62)

REFLECTING ON THE CONTENT OF THE FIRST COURSEPACK OF MY PHD JOURNEY

1)INTRODUCTION

To improve my theoretical knowledge in my area of expertise, I enrolled in a Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) program in Global Health and Health Systems at a university that offers the flexibility of taking courses while continuing to work. The start of this program consists of becoming familiar with the skills required and the rules applicable to quality academic and scientific writing.

To facilitate students' access to these rules, the course's instructors have co-written a course pack that contains the theoretical bases of quality academic writing. I have explored this booklet and am pleased to reflect on its contents.

During my reading, my attention was particularly drawn to the chapters that cover essay writing, punctuation, plagiarism, the style guide, and the use of the Chicago Manual of Style, as well as the use of Latin abbreviations and expressions. The following lines are meant to share my reflection on what I read.

2) ESSAY WRITING

The course was introduced with a chapter covering essay writing, with a specific focus on academic writing. The instructors explained and provided details of what could be specificities someone should pay attention to in order to deliver quality essay writing. They described the different steps towards essay writing as follows: early start-up, which includes the definition of the question, as well as the task analysis and the drafting of the plan, and then topic research, organization of ideas, the actual essay writing up, followed by the referencing and editing, and handing in.

This description differs from my personal experience. From my point of view, to perform any work of this type, it is better to begin researching the topic first and eventually draft the plan, organize the ideas, and so forth. The actual write-up comes after these steps since well-performed research on the topic of interest adds more context around the idea(s) under consideration.

Furthermore, another critical point to keep in mind is when the course instructors asserted “not to try to write an essay from beginning to end (especially not in a single study session) but rather begin with what is ready to be written - a plan, a sentence” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 11). This assertion speaks to me particularly. Indeed, although I registered for this program in December 2022, I only started my first response paper for my first course more than a year later. I realized that I took all this time to start because it occurred to me that I wanted to write my paper straight from beginning to end. This led to procrastination and delays, showing that my initial approach to starting this program was the least appropriate.

3) PUNCTUATIONS

Once you start writing down your paper, it is necessary to give special importance to punctuation. More than in speaking, punctuation improves the flow and smoothness of writing. It helps to clarify the meaning of a sentence, which can thus change depending on whether punctuation has been used or not. The use of punctuation follows diverse rules, just as there are different types of punctuation. Knowing these rules ensures that the right punctuation is used at the right time and the right place and gives the expected meaning.

Going through this chapter allowed me to deconstruct some preconceived ideas. Examples of these ideas include the fact that I have always thought scare brackets should surround ellipses or that it was necessary to punctuate with commas the end of bullet points with listed items regardless of the context.

On the other hand, I still feel confused about some aspects of punctuation. This is the case with the differences in the rules for using punctuation depending on whether we use American or British English. This reflects the need to master the chosen style to ensure that what is written means what is expected.

4) PLAGIARISM

The next step in the academic writing process is to ensure that you do not replicate something that has previously been done. Plagiarism is a threat to academic work. It reflects the lack of honesty and the lack of recognition of efforts from colleagues and fellows in advancing knowledge. It can lead to a lack of creativity or laziness and the advancement of knowledge is threatened if vigorous measures are not taken,

The definition proposed by Cleenewerck & Gulma, recognizes plagiarism as being “when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (2024, 34.) contributes to placing particular emphasis on the honesty that should guide the use of information not coming primarily from someone as an author, whether in academic writing or not.

The instructors also elaborated on the consequences of plagiarism and provided a list of available tools to give full credit to efforts made by colleagues whose previous work inspires us. These tools are referred to as in-text references (including paraphrasing), the use of a list of cited works at the end of the text, and so forth.

That said, it is necessary to notice that some information is seen as public knowledge. Therefore, using it does not require citation. Some of them are well-known in my area of expertise. An example is the information on the fact that vaccination is one of the most cost-effective public health interventions able to prevent disease at the lowest cost. Nowadays, this assertion is widely disseminated and does not need a source to be cited. Some advice to determine whether a citation is required includes applying the following basic rule:

“If it is repeated in many different sources that you have, then you can assume it is common knowledge” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 37).

5) STYLE GUIDE AND USE OF CHICAGO STYLE

Among the factors that contribute to improving the quality of academic writing is style. For an author, adopting a style is a way to ensure coherence and consistency between their different works. Moreover, as Cleenewerck & Gulma said, for collaborative work involving contributions from several authors, it is even more critical to observe the guidelines on the use of style to ensure consistency between each author’s style (2024, 41). The criteria they have listed as part of the style guides include, among others:

- the preferred sentence lengths
- the manuscript layout
- font usage
- the use of symbols and

- voice preferences (active vs. passive)

To name just a few.

The Chicago Style is the recommended style. It is a combo of two writing styles described in two manuals, namely, the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS), 2003, and the Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, 1996. These two books describe three classes of stylistic approaches: page formatting, use of end/footnotes, use of abbreviations, capitalization, compound words, dates and numbers, and italics/quotation marks.

Although these categories are all relevant, the ones that describe the rules for using italics/quotation marks seem to have caught my attention. I believe they describe concepts that contribute to improving a text's structure, its understanding, and its flow.

According to Cleenewerck & Gulma, Italics and quotation marks are used to highlight words, note and translate words in a language foreign to a reader, indicate irony (scare quotes), or mark words and letters that are referred to as words, not to the meaning they convey (2024, 47).

6) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

As a native French speaker and a scientist attracted by Latinism, the root of the French language, this paragraph particularly caught my attention. Abbreviations and Latin expressions can be used to enhance writing skills. Even though Cleenewerck & Gulma pointed out the preference "in business, formal, and technical writing, to use the English equivalent of the abbreviation to avoid misinterpretation by (...) readers" (2024, 59), I strongly believe, building on my Francophone background, that the use of abbreviations and Latin expressions brings an additional touch to the beauty of a text.

These abbreviations and expressions are varied, however, they must be chosen and used appropriately.

7) CONCLUSION

Having walked through this first coursepack of my Ph.D. program, I feel like I have gained more comfort and sufficient confidence to advance the next steps of my studies. From now on, I will engage confidently in writing several papers throughout the program cycle. This is expected to culminate with the writing of my dissertation at the end of the program. It is then important to familiarize myself with good practices in academic writing and stay away from misbehavior such as plagiarism and bad use of the rules of styles.

I will pay special attention to some of the guidelines that have been provided to me, including tips for effective essay writing, proper use of punctuation, or adapted rules for

citations. All of them, if used well, will ensure a good mastery and delivery of quality academic writing throughout my studies.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.